

An Assessment of the Effects of Higher Education on Nation Building

Prof. Adeyemo, K.A., Alhaji Salami, Olagoke L. and Alabi, Olufemi Abidoye

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Editor's Note

In December 1963, the United Nations General Assembly adopted resolution to explore ways and means of supporting national efforts for the eradication of illiteracy, through a world campaign, and any other appropriate measures, both financial and non-financial. Following this resolution, UNESCO convened a number of regional conferences to study the problem of illiteracy in different countries. In April, 1964, it convened an international committee of experts on literacy, which suggested the selective approach that would launch literacy programmes in organized sections of the economy, particularly in such areas where people in employment would need literacy for their regular work; the implication was that national development plans embracing economic and general educational considerations should include programmes for functional management. The concept of functional management was thus formulated within a context in which the world was ready for a new approach to literacy. Its historical roots portray it as born by the necessity for urgent development. This places functional literacy in the position of endearment to all developing countries as a method of promoting adjustment to desirable change, so that all peoples in a development situation may grow to become the agents and the objects of their own development.

One of the great aims of functional management makes its adherent a better of what he is. Thus, its adoption helps anybody engaged in any development-oriented work to become more competent and better equipped for his work. Thus the farmer, artisan, industrial worker, trader, teacher, office worker and in fact, anybody in a development situation, require functionality to become better able to perform their tasks. The fact is that the recasting of the modes of functioning in a modern economy, the creation of a new mentality, the process of adaptation to the industrial environment and the ability to meet its technical demands, all require some level of functional management.

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Prof. Adeyemo, K.A.

Department of Management and Accounting

Lead City University, Ibadan

Alhaji Salami, Olagoke L.

Accountant General of Oyo State

A Doctoral Student at University of Ibadan

and

Alabi, Olufemi Abidoye

Department of Banking and Finance

Osun State College of Technology, Esa Oke, Osun State

Abstract

This paper assessed the effects of Higher Education on nation building. The paper established the fact that higher educations have empowered recipient to contribute greatly to political, social and economically development of Nigeria Higher Education and Nigeria's manpower development.

The paper concludes that higher education is critical to development of nations. It is a tool used for the integration of the individual into the society so that he can achieve self realization, develop national consciousness, promote unity and strive for social, economic, political, scientific, cultural and technological progress. The paper recommends the needs for quality management to a university administration system.

Introduction

The National Policy on Education (2012) acknowledges the role of education in helping Nigerian citizens attain the global national goals as stated in the National Development Plan.

Fafunwa (1979) defines education as "the aggregate of all the processes by which a child or adult develops the abilities, attitudes and other forms of behaviour which are of positive value to the society in which he lives, that is to say, it is a process of disseminating knowledge either to ensure social control or to guarantee rational direction of the society or both."

FRN (1998) states that education as a variable instrument for national development should foster the worth and development of the individuals, for each individual's sake, and for the general development of the society.

However to enable education achieve the stated goals the philosophy of education was based in a number of issues which include the provision, of equal educational opportunities for all citizens at the various levels of formal education namely; primary, secondary and tertiary levels.

These levels are expected to fully develop and equip Nigerian citizens with relevant knowledge and skills in the economy.

The university which is part of the tertiary levels of education is the main focus of this paper. This is predicated on the fact that the university is the highest educational institution charged with the responsibility of manpower development for the full realization of the aspirations of Nigerian citizens for self-reliance and society development.

World Bank (1994) emphasised this when it states that tertiary education has the main responsibility for training a country's professional personnel including the managers, scientists, engineers, and technicians who participate in the development, adaptation and diffusion of innovation in the economy.

William Saint (2005) in his paper 'Higher Education and development states'

Education rightly linked to economic and social development is a toll to development. It is simultaneously a driver and a beneficiary of economic growth — — But economic thrive

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and basic education expands only when they are supported by an education system that takes significant numbers of students beyond the basic cycle including to university completion. To ensure its sustainability an education system needs to be balanced. It must be capable of producing students at different levels with qualifications that respond to labour market needs, generating a steady supply of skilled workers, technicians, professionals, managers and leaders. Without such balance and diversity in education, the prospect for growth, social cohesion, more equitable economic distribution and reduction of poverty will remain largely out of reach.

(Saint 2005) In the changing universe of today, education has been defined by many scholars, research institutions and organisations from different perspectives.

The International Standard Classification of education (1985) design defines education as an organised and sustained communication designed to bring about learning where communication' requires a relationship between two or more persons involving the transfer of information. "Organised" is intended to mean planned in a pattern or sequence with established aims or curricula. Sustained" is intended to mean that the learning experience has the elements of duration and continuity Learning is taken as any change in knowledge', skills, attitudes, behaviour, understanding and or capabilities which can be retained and cannot be ascribed to physical growth or to the development of inherited behavioural patterns. Training is learning experience that leads to the acquisition of a skill'.

Education is the formal process by which society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills, customs and values from one generation to another by, for example, instruction in schools.

The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 2002) defines education as an indispensable means of realising other human rights. As an empowerment right, education is the primary vehicle by which economically and socially marginalised adults and children can lift themselves out of poverty and obtain the means to participate fully in their communities. Education has a vital role in empowering women, safeguarding children from

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exploitative and hazardous labour and sexual exploitation, promoting human rights and democracy, protecting the environment, and controlling population growth.

Increasingly, education is recognised as one of the best financial investments states can make. Education, as described above contains two domains. First, 'regular education and 'adult education' and both can comprise formal education for which registration is a requirement, and the non-formal education characterised by the absence of registration requirements.

Education is, therefore, seen in this context as an intrinsic value with attendant benefits enshrined in the promotion, attainment, and sustenance of the fundamental human rights of all citizens. It is a powerful instrument known to man for social progress and improvement. In his own view, Ate (2000), as quoted by Emunemu (2004), sees this type of education as a proposed framework for achieving EFA in the country; the lifelong learning must be seen as a procedure which will allow for proper integration of formal, non-formal and informal learning into an abundant life practice at home, at work and in the larger society.

The Nature of University Education in Nigeria

- Universities all over the world are charged with three responsibilities namely, teaching research and development and extension. According to Sanda (1992) the objective of universities is the pursuit of truth and the liberation of the mind through research, intellectual debates and learning. All Nigeria universities have discrete roles and function which they perform as conferred on them during establishment. These roles and functions are expected to guide the activities of the universities. Nevertheless FRN (1998) assigned the following responsibilities to university education;

- (a) Intensifying and diversifying its programmes for the development of high level manpower with the content of the needs of the nations.
- (b) Making professional course contents to reflect our national requirements;
- (c) Making all students, as part of a general programme of all-round improvement in university education, to offer study courses such as history of ideas, philosophy of knowledge and

nationalism. A number of factors characterise Nigerian universities as a result of its highly structured and rigid nature.

The highly formal nature of Nigerian universities has made the adoption of the conventional face-to-face mode of instruction by many universities discriminatory. It has limited the scope of effectiveness and operations of university education to only those who are opportuned to be admitted into the universities. This is in contradiction to the provision of equal access to education opportunities for all citizens of the country at Primary, Secondary and Tertiary levels both inside and outside the formal school system as stimulated by the FRN (1990).

As the US National Centre for Public and Fundamental Education states in its special report, higher education has the national responsibilities for nation building: (i) to provide graduates with economic skills at large with an effective and efficient global increase in demand in which corporations reach across national geographical divides in search of new markets, more efficient production, and less costly labour; and, (ii) to close the achievement gap between those students in this country who are advantaged educationally, culturally, and economically and those who are not."

There are several steps that must be taken to meet these two fundamental responsibilities. As some experts have stated, these will include the implementation of the 2006 Plan of Action for the Second Decade of Education for Africa, a document which has been adopted by the African Union. This Plan of Action "spells out the ingredients for effective, relevant, efficient and revitalised higher education for Africa in a bid to make it globally competitive." They include:

- Encouraging greater mobility of academics, researchers, staff and students; and the recognition of qualifications from and by the different regions of Africa through the harmonisation of degree structures.
- Establishing an African Higher Education and Research Space that will pay serious attention to institutional and national Quality Assurance systems and promote high level relevant research and postgraduate training tailored towards solving the daily problems which plague African communities.

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- Adopting and adapting Open and Distance Learning as instructional delivery mechanisms in Sub-Saharan Africa as has been done in other continents of the world if Africa is to significantly raise its tertiary education enrolment ratio from the current 6% (achieved through the face-to-face mode) to at least 50% within the next 5 years;
- Using Information and Communication Technologies effectively for instructional delivery, professional communication, to develop, produce, acquire and distribute knowledge, skills and competencies across the continent as fast as they are available;
- Building human resource base that will seek newer and effective ways to combat diseases, reduce energy costs and address climate change;
- Creating centres of excellence within each region of the continent to develop robust postgraduate studies and develop strong research base with global competitive advantage.
- Seeking opportunities for collaboration and partnership on equal and mutually beneficial platforms with the international world including universities in other continents, development partners, organisation and agencies genuinely interested in higher education in Africa.

Aina (2010) correctly observed, "African universities operate at the fourth and fifth tiers of global knowledge production." As old and current experiences have shown, even when a country has huge natural resources, without the development of human resources, a country with natural resources will continue to be subservient to countries with the developed human capability and capacity to extract, refine and use those natural resources. The story of Africa - a continent that is perhaps the most blessed among other continents in terms of natural resources, but one that has refused to fully develop its human resources and place these human resources at the centre of her development agenda - is a sad one. Top on the list of the fundamental crisis of the continent is the crisis of higher education. Olugbemi (2012), Secretary General Association of African Universities stated:

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"The emerging global landscape being drawn by recent developments has shown very clearly that knowledge capability and capacity, rather than natural resources, is the greatest determinant of a country's entry into, and effective participation in, global competitiveness. It goes without saying, therefore, that higher education contributes significantly to the political, scientific, technological, economic, social and human development of any country. This is even more so for the developing countries of Africa, a continent of about one billion people characterised by the poorest countries in the world, with the world's highest illiteracy rates, lowest participation rates in higher education, huge capacity development needs, over 20 million seeking employment annually with the youth constituting 60% of the unemployed, and a massive demand for tertiary education."

Education is critical to the development of nations. It is an antidote to poverty and leveier in the emerging knowledge society. Nigeria's prosperity depends solely on a well-educated citizenry national life. Developing economies, such as ours, can only fast-track and/or leap frog their growth through targeted research and development. A practical way to do this is to do what is generically referred to as reverse engineering. It is these institutions that must provide the road map to circumvent those road blocks to indigenous technology enhancement necessary for driving innovation and development of the nation.

The nation must be prepared to invest heavily in the higher education cutting across both the public and private. The research facilities must orchestrate the brain power of the staff, take responsibility for training new generation of talents and participate in the transformation of the nation's S&T base. Science brings imagination on theoretical speculations as well as on practical problems and critical decisions, allowing people to analyze the prevent (and future) situations, make sounder choices, and invest their resources more wisely. At the same time, the benefits of science and technology are not reaching a major part of the world's people and we need to remove these barriers. Ibidapo-Obe, (2012).

We need a coherent national S&T strategy with framework developed in consultation with the Nigerian Academy of Science and other academies to specify the national priorities for research and development with the appropriate funding commitment (at about 1.5% of the GDP annually),

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and include merit-based support for basic science and recognise the need for higher level training to develop, as much as possible, natural competence in selected frontier areas of science and technology that are most suitable for sustainable economic development and social well being. This is the path that China took some 50 years ago.

According to the OECD's head of education and statistics, Andreas Schleicher, China has an education system that is overtaking many Western countries because the idea that education is the key to mobility and success is so deep rooted. On a trip to a poor province in China, he noted that schools were often the most impressive buildings.

In October 7, 2010 an article published in Time magazine, was befittingly titled: "The Real Challenge from China: Its People, Not its Currency", recognising that China's greatest advantage lies in the knowledge it brings to the table. Taiwan is another country that has long exploited education for economic gain. Taiwan is a barren rock in a typhoon-prone sea with no natural resources at all. It even imports sand and gravel from China for construction. Yet it has the 4 largest financial reserves in the world because rather than digging up the ground and mining whatever it finds, Taiwan mines the most valuable and only truly renewable source in the world today- its people,

Taiwan understands that a country will increasingly have to live by its knowledge and that this depends on the quality of education available and received. Investments in education and human resources have been key factors in the rapid economic growth of South Korea over the last 4 decades.

In 2002, 71% of South Korea's GDP was spent on education, including research and development. Interestingly, apart from Government investment, over the past 40 years the private sector has also contributed significantly to research and development in South Korea, which has resulted in a corresponding increase in indigenous innovation.

Universities/Higher Education as Innovation Hubs

Universities as knowledge producing institutions must constitute the 'hub' for knowledge disseminations and applications. Higher Education Institutions educate and train new generation

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of S&T talent, and perform research and development; therefore these are critical for expanding national S&T capacities. Using science to address the challenges of the development means carrying out relevant research, putting the results into practice through technological innovation and generally using them to inform public policy.

The nation must gradually move away from a consumer to a producer nation.

The obstacles (including the WTO GATT Agreements, the WMQ Montreal Protocols and others which we have been committed to without our clear understanding of the implications, the high level discussions on climate change) must be carefully reviewed, revised and those that are inimical to the nation must be abrogated. These are the challenges and opportunities for the universities to make impact on the society. What has been and what remains as the stake of Universities in this quest for excellence? It is in the production in learning and character of young scientists and technologists that will improve the capacities of S&T human pool.

Higher Institutions are set up essentially for the 'public good' in respective of ownership be it public or private. The key attributes are: Research (R), Knowledge propagation/teaching (K), and Community service/innovation (I).

Research is the process of creating new knowledge or new insights on knowledge, or unlocking knowledge. Knowledge is generally defined as the high quality, preferably policy relevant information, both in codified and tacit forms often location-specific. Innovations are new and renewed products and processes outcomes through the use of knowledge. In short the product of these institutions will be the diverse of economy.

It is important therefore to understand that these institutions are not set up simply as diploma and certificate mills to produce students in learning centres, but primarily to do research, and disseminate findings and propagate innovation through the society. The core values must include excellence, transparency, integrity, merit, and relevance. Some best practices are evolving in these institutions as a result of the renewed efforts to revitalize the quality of outcomes in view of several system shortcomings and vices including admitting beyond the carrying capacity, sorting, racketeering, masquerading, settlement, and impersonation etc. through accreditation of programmes and institutions as well as ranking for global competitiveness.

These emerging best practices are now classified under the broad core responsibilities viz. Research and development, teaching and community service.

Research and Development

1. Every university should have a research policy to be backed up with local grants and supported by funds from the ETF Research Funds, National Research Foundation as well as bilateral and international organisations.
2. Make research relevant to society and community needs.
3. Develop innovative funding ideas through partnering with industries and organised private sector.
4. Invite annually, as a policy, a well-known academic/scholar as an external examiner from one of the identified best 200 ranked universities in the world.
5. Advertise for and recruit globally academic positions.

Teaching

- I. Leverage on e-learning facilities to update the learning system and access to the various e-teacher activities.
2. Update and re-align the curriculum to reflect the requirements of employers through the introduction of entrepreneurial programmes for all students.
3. Ensure that the Academic Boards of Senate consist of knowledgeable and enthusiastic members including the community leaders.
4. Embark on a deliberate strategy to recruit and retain world class scholars. Academic staff salaries need not be uniform even within and between staff grades.
5. Establish an institution-wide committee of the academic board to oversee quality and standards of instruction.
6. Introduce co-operative education system for all professional disciplines.

Community Service

1. Enthroned accountability and transparency in the institution management including fund raising and endowment activities.
2. Sustain peace on campus through constant dialogue with the various unions and cordial relationship with the host communities by meeting their expectations. (Corporate Social Responsibility-CSR, to community schools, hospitals and other public projects must annually be provided for in the budget).
3. Networking on special thematic areas within and outside the country and interface with other non-educational institutions and organisations.
4. Establishment of a veritable consulting service.
5. Establishment of Research, Development and Technology Parks to showcase continuously academic staff enduring works.

Challenges Facing University Education in Nigeria

University education in Nigeria has made tremendous achievement in attaining the goals of national development. These are visible in the area of manpower development, research findings, and the adoption of these findings. Despite these achievement, university education still face in a lot of challenge that have bearing on the highly structure and conventional nature of education at the tertiary levels. These challenges have hindered the realisation of some of the national policies and there is need to address these challenges urgently.

One of the major challenges is the inability of universities to absorb pressures from enrolment expansion. There is a dire competition for university education in Nigeria leading to more candidate than the universities can admit.

Ndem (1981) noted that yearly, Nigeria universities turn back over fifty thousand virtually qualified student for admission because of lack of facilities to accommodate them. Echerue (1984) noted that no degree of expansion of existing conventional universities can make them accommodate the impending explosion of university students. Asogua (1995) deduced that since the 1990s. over 78% of candidates who apply for admission into Nigeria universities are not admitted owing to lack of spaces.

According to the World Bank (1999), "successful development entails more than investing in physical capital, or closing the gap in capital. It also entails acquiring and using knowledge as well as closing the gaps in knowledge". Thus, to successfully confront the challenges of development, a developing country must undertake three major tasks:

- Acquired and adapt global knowledge and create knowledge locally.
- Invest in human capital to increase the ability to absorb and use knowledge; and
- Invest in technologies to facilitate both acquisition and the absorption of knowledge.

The challenges of access, quality, and cost remain dominant at all levels of education. We must therefore pay much more attention to the quality of our primary education so that by the time our children gain admission into institutions of higher learning such as this, they will be better prepared to receive the type of instruction that will enable them to compete on a global level that is much more complex than the type of foundation we are presently laying for them.

We must train our children to be intellectually curious. We must teach them to question and to probe, to be inquisitive. To be curious, if we do not teach them to question, to probe and to be inquisitive, then we cannot achieve the kind of results that will enable us to gain and sustain momentum in the global economy. Curiosity stimulates an inquiring mind and an inquiring mind cannot resist the urge to challenge the status quo. Every notable human endeavour was underpinned by curiosity.

Cornia quoting Wali (2004) states that:

"Within the Nigeria education system, more than a million primary school learners who need access to secondary education could not gain access. This in addition to the desire to train more than 40,000 teachers. Equally of relevance is the desire of more than one million secondary school learners to gain admission to the university. For the years 2004 alone, one million applied for admissions out of which there were only 100,000 available spaces"

In the same vein John Daniel, former UNESCO Assistant Director General and now President of Commonwealth of Learning (COL) who summarised Africa education problem as "eternal triangle of education" that consists of the three vectors access, quality and cost. He explained further while addressing all African Ministers of Education Conference on open learning in 2004, that,

"the problem you face with conventional methods, is the eternal triangle constraint, increase access by increasing class size, people will accuse you of lowering quality. If you try to raise quality by putting more resources in the classroom, you will raise cost and if you try to cut cost, you will often reduce access and quality at the same time".

Another major challenge is unbridled population growth. Nigeria, with a population of 167 million, has an annual growth rate of 2.1 % (a reduction of 1% over the last 4 years or so). A good target for population growth rate should not exceed 1% per annum. The G7 countries that we target in 2020 have 0% growth rate or less and in fact have to supplement their work force with encouraging migration from less developed countries (a new wave of brain drain) The current Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is \$248 billion with a GDP per capita of \$1,660; the growth rate is put at about 6%

even though the financial meltdown has further depressed this growth to about 5.8%. However in order to achieve the objectives of Vision 20:2020 the economy GDP must grow at 7.25% annually. A clear challenge here is low productivity and a total dependence on imports).

One of the greatest challenge facing Nigeria and making it difficult for good quality education that is capable of bringing about sustainable development is inadequate funding by federal, state and local governments to the extent that funding has been in response to conditionality imposed by international financial institutions (IFIs). In 1997 and 2000 statistics show that federal government expenditure on education was below 10% of overall expenditure. It noticed that, the national expenditure on education cannot be computed because various states expenditure on education cannot be determined, in relation to the UNESCO recommendation of 26% of national budgets. A sustainable amount of fund must be allocated to education.

Another problem of Education in Nigerian schools today is the politicisation of Education; which seriously affected the development of education. Today many educational institutions are opened and run in many states on political ground or other flimsy reasons. In Nigerian schools today admission in universities, colleges, polytechnics, monotechnics, secondary and primary schools are sometimes guided by politicians not academic performance. Parent today used their political offices or influences for the education of their children.

A sensitive issue that crippled the development of education is the manner and the why the politician influence the recruitment exercise of teachers.

Many people today are after securing job for their children just to have meal ticket not bothering whether their wards qualified or not.

Poverty and Fall in Standard

Acquisition of Education knowledge is supposed to help us fight against-poverty, ignorance and disease. The process of acquiring this well desired knowledge has gradually turned money spinning venture for many of those in dire need of the knowledge and skill. It is now a source of exploitation from the service seekers with little or no consideration for quality of service rendered and facilities on ground, and made an offer for the highest bidder.

A trend which has cut across all levels of education, from nursery school to tertiary institutions.

The concept, "poverty", refers to a situation and process of serious deprivation or lack of resources and materials necessary for living within a minimum standard conducive for human dignity and wellbeing NEST, (1992).

Admission and being in school today is merely an ability to pay what is demanded in monetary terms by school operators and not on what could be offered academically. And this in essence widens the scope of poverty prevalence as well as the gap between the rich and the poor which education is designed to bridge. Little wonder why graduates from many of the institutions exhibits ignorance towards societal realities and lack of creativity, due to the inadequacies associated with the learning and training process which is also observed to be partly because many of those that offer this service do so with greed.

The problem of educational development in the world not only in Nigeria is that of responsibility and control, the conflict between the Federal, State and Local Government in the management of education at various level is one of the prominent problem of educational development in Nigeria. Take for example, the control of primary education is neither fully in the hand of federal government, nor state or local government and this is a great barrier for effective educational development at basic level.

In Nigeria today, one should not be thinking of unavailable teachers but instability. The unstable condition of teaching staff in Nigerian primary and secondary schools has drastically crippled the system. The question is why instability? the answer is that, the condition of service does not favor them to stay in the profession and as such always looking for alternative.

Another critical area that hinder development of education today is indiscipline, this is manifested in examination malpractices, secret cult menace, corruption etc. Crises in our schools today has led to "brain-drain", students of today are no longer interested in academic excellence but when would I pass out from the schools.

Poor parenting/guidance is another cause, many parent lack caring, protection and guidance, and as such no adequate provision of basic needs for their children to up-keep him or her to meet the challenges of life, in accordance with the laws of the land. Many parent have today bring

innovation that are not encouraging but paving ways to examination malpractices in order to brighten the chances of their wards in qualifying examination to higher institutions. My investigation revealed that some examination centres exist in this nation where parent are paying money for qualifying their wards to pass SSCE, WAEC / NECO JAMB.

Education-For-All (EFA)

At the meeting of World conference on EFA at Jomtien Thailand in 1990, participating governments acknowledge and recognise that education-for-all must meet basic learning needs so as to develop self-reliance in meeting the needs of the people in their respective countries by the year 2000. The conference, among other things:

- i. recalls that education is a fundamental right for all people; women and men of all ages, throughout the world.
- ii. understands that education can help ensure a safer, healthier, more prosperous and environmentally sound world, and simultaneously contribute to social, economic, and cultural progress, tolerance, and international co-operation,
- iii. knows that education is an indispensable key to, though not a sufficient condition for, personal and social improvement.
- iv. recognises that traditional knowledge and indigenous cultural heritage have a value and validity in their own right and a capacity to both define and promote development.
- v. acknowledges that, overall, the current provision of education is seriously deficient and it must be made more relevant and qualitatively improved and made universally available.
- vi. recognises that sound basic education is fundamental to the strengthening of higher levels of education, scientific and technological literacy and capacity and thus to self-reliant development,
- vii. Recognises the necessity to give present and coming generations an expanded vision of, and a renewed commitment to, basic education to address the scale and complexity of the challenge (UNESCO, 2000b).

Conclusion

Every university/higher institution must engender its own unique character in sustaining the academic culture, in terms of inquisitions and dogged search for the truth; it is important to encourage students to organise themselves in science and nature clubs, literary societies, volunteer groups etc.

It is clear that there is an urgent need to revitalize higher education in Nigeria through policies and reforms, programmes, pedagogy, and teaching tools, training of teachers as well as research in education. Since the wealth of nation is measured by the content and quality of knowledge inherent and latent in that society.

Recommendations

- That government should endeavour to implement all higher educational programmes policies and blueprint, as entrenched in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Other national Policies relating to education and finding most especially all international declarations, conventions and resolutions to which Nigeria is a signatory must be respected and implemented.
- That government, in implementing higher educational programmes,, should have budget lines for all programmes intended to be implemented while it accepts other funds including loans and grant as complementary and not as core funds,
- That, Nigerians should endeavour to encourage and assist others to know better than they found them e.g. as literate, make one person literate starting from your immediate environment.
- That higher institutions of learning should ensure that innovative approaches are put in place to enrich teaching, training and the conduct of research.
- That all structures, be strengthened to accommodate all higher educational programmes practices be it in theory or in practice.

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- That adult and non-formal education should be included in all developmental initiatives and social programmes as an essential contribution to economic prosperity, sustainable development, social cohesion, peaceful resolution of conflicts and political stability.
- That all organs of information dissemination e.g. radio, TV, computer and bill boards should engage higher educational programmes experts in the positive maximization of the valuable space, air time and resources at their disposal in the re-orientation of listeners, readers and users of such medium, most especially in contemporary and global issues.
- That all donors, bilateral and international development partners should show sincere commitments and support and fund higher educational programmes without prejudice.
- To all intellectuals, we must accept that without education we can not bring about change, positive change for that matter. We must also recognise and accept NFE strategies as problem solving tools.
- That the organised private sector should be more focused and more visible in supporting on the job training of not only their staff, but also intervene in curriculum process of formal institutions so that products of these institutions would fit into their programme of activities. We need to close ranks and benefit from each other.
- Institutions should also move closer to the community, evolve participatory approach in the identification of courses and development of curriculum as these will allow for learning contents to reflect desired needs of the entire target population of the institutions, as no man is an island.

University education in Nigeria today needs a total overhauling and restructuring to improve the effective performance of the system hence, university administrators NUC stakeholder to put all hands on deck to finding lasting solution to reposition Nigerian universities to be the first among equals globally.

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